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Transfer Learning-Based Prediction of Heating Energy Consumption Using Urban Building Energy Models (UBEM)

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Abstract. To estimate the energy demand of buildings, machine learning (ML) using datasets generated by Urban Building Energy Modeling (UBEM) has emerged as a potent approach. However, collecting large training datasets for each urban context is challenging, and developing large UBEMs for each city is too resource-intensive. Transfer learning (TL) can address these limitations by transferring knowledge from an existing model to train a model in target cities with limited datasets. In this paper, we present an approach for TL-based prediction of heating energy consumption on an urban scale based on three existing UBEMs of cities with different climatic conditions and thermal characteristics of buildings. Our experiments show that TL does provide better estimation compared to training ML models from scratch. Furthermore, our results suggest that this gain in accuracy is even higher if the target city has a substantially low number of buildings to train an ML model.

1. Introduction

Accurately estimating the energy consumption of buildings at the urban scale is essential for decision-makers to take proactive retrofit measures. Machine learning (ML) methods can facilitate the estimation of energy consumption with high prediction performance and lower computational costs. In particular, ML models such as artificial neural networks (ANN), (Li et al., 2019; Li et al., 2015), support vector machines (SVM) (Guo *et al.*, 2018; Liu *et al.*, 2020), multi-layer perceptron (MLP) (Ding *et al.*, 2018) and deep learning models (DL) (Fan *et al.*, 2019) are commonly used for energy consumption predictions. In these ML models, the prediction performance is strongly influenced by the size of the training dataset (Fan *et al.*, 2020), as larger datasets provide more diverse samples, offer better generalizability, and reduce overfitting. However, in an urban context, training data (i.e. materials, occupancy, internal loads) is usually difficult to obtain. Training with insufficiently sized datasets leads to overfitting due to limited diversity and high variance. As a solution, transfer learning (TL) can utilize the knowledge acquired from other tasks to improve the performance of a target task (Pan and Yang, 2010; Weiss, Khoshgoftaar, and Wang, 2016). TL allows models to apply existing knowledge from one domain to another, which is particularly beneficial when data for the target task is scarce. Specific to urban-scale predictions, TL can transfer knowledge from a well-trained model for a specific city to a new city that has limited data resources. This allows ML-based forecasting models to deliver accurate results even for cities with significantly smaller data sets. As such, TL can enable the effective use of limited data resources and improve the accuracy and applicability of energy prediction models for urban buildings in real-world scenarios.

In the literature, TL has been widely used for the hourly prediction of building energy consumption. Gao et al. (2020) applied TL with deep learning models for predicting office building energy consumption. Chen et al. (2020) used TL with deep neural networks to model

predictive control of HVAC and natural ventilation. Fang et al. (2021) proposed a hybrid deep TL strategy for short-term energy prediction using Long Short Memory and Domain Adversarial Neural Networks. Fan et al. (2020) utilized TL for 24-hour predictions of building energy demand. Li et al. (2021) developed a TL-based ANN model for one-hour-ahead prediction of building energy demand. While TL showed promising results for hourly prediction, such knowledge transfer between cities for urban-scale energy consumption prediction has not been tackled yet with TL.

In this paper, we propose a TL-based ML approach for the prediction of building heating energy consumption on the urban scale. Our approach is based on existing bottom-up, physics-based Urban Building Energy Models (UBEMs) of three cities with different climatic characteristics (Figure 1). Using these UBEMs, we first calculated annual energy use and developed datasets for training and testing. Following this, we developed three multilayer perceptron (MLP) models for each city to predict annual heating energy consumption. Then, we implemented TL from the source city to target cities for MLP models. We evaluated the comparative prediction performances of models with TL and without TL (Experiment 1). Then, we investigated the effect of dataset sizes of target cities on transfer learning (Experiment 2).

2. Methodology

Figure 1: The Main Steps of Our Methodology

In the study, we train and test our model using the data sets of three cities in Türkiye. Our approach applies TL on an ML model of the source city Ankara (ANK), which was already trained with a rich dataset and has achieved good predictive performance, to two other ML models of two target cities, Izmir (IZM) and Erzurum (ERZ) with significantly smaller dataset sizes. Our methodology consists of the following steps.

2.1 Step I: Dataset Preparation and Pre-processing

The first step is to develop training and testing data sets for the three cities that have different numbers of buildings and climate characteristics (Table 1). We will use D_{ANK} , D_{IZM} , and D_{ERZ} to describe these three datasets. Our ML models aim to use input features that describe a thermal zone in a building to predict an output feature which is the zone's heating energy use ($Q_{heating}$) (Figure 2). We used 21 features that describe the zones/buildings: envelope construction characteristics (u values for wall, roof, ground, windows, window SHGC), infiltration, boiler efficiency (n_{boiler}), internal loads (people (PPL), equipment (EPD), lighting (LPD)), setpoints ($T_{heating}$), window-wall-ratio and sky exposures (in four directions), and geometric features (formFactor, verticalPosition).

To calculate $Q_{heating}$, we used UBEMs of the selected neighborhoods that were developed previously by Halacli et al. (2023) using the input features described above in three cities. We calculated $Q_{heating}$ through simulations with EnergyPlus 9.2, with the typical meteorological year (TMY) weather files of each city. All UBEMs were developed using the 3D building models as well as other semantic data acquired from the municipality records. Where available, existing data sources were used; otherwise, data augmentation with kernel density estimation was applied to generate synthetic data.

Table 1: Climatic Conditions and Dataset Sizes in the Three Selected Cities

	$N_{buildings}$	N_{zones}	Köppen climate type	Heating Degree Days (HDD)* (°C)	Cooling Degree Days (CDD)* (°C)	Mean Dry Bulb Temp. (DBT)* (°C)	Glob. Horiz. Rad. (GHR)* (W/m ²)
ANK	593	64522	Csa (cold winter, hot & dry summer)	2499.47	259.57	13.37	197.88
IZM	608	6076	Csa (mild winter, hot & dry summer)	1344.82	505.67	17.84	198.27
ERZ	590	6410	Dfb (cold winter, dry & cool summer)	5267.85	83.22	4.69	188.21

*: calculated from TMY weather files. HDD and GHR are also used for combined MLP models

Figure 2: The distribution of input parameters and output parameter ($Q_{heating}$) in source and target datasets

In the MLPs, we scaled the numerical input parameters with the standard scaler (using “(value-mean)/standard-deviation”). We used 15% of the datasets for testing and 85% of datasets for training and cross-validation. To evaluate the impact of the dataset size on transfer learning, we performed experiments by subsampling the training and validation datasets. We will use $D_{IZM\beta}$, and $D_{ERZ\beta}$ to denote subsampled datasets of D_{IZM} and D_{ERZ} , where $\beta \in \{10, 30, 50\}$, denoting the percentage of subsampling.

2.2 Step II: Source ML Models

We developed three source MLP models for the three cities to predict zone $Q_{heating}$ and to apply transfer learning. An MLP is an ANN composed of small processing units, called neurons. A neuron’s value at layer l (a_i^l) can be described as:

$$a_i^l = \sigma \left(\left[\sum_{j=1}^n a_j^{l-1} \cdot w_{ij}^{l1} \right] + b_i^l \right),$$

where σ is a nonlinear function, w_{ij}^l and b_i^l denote the neuron’s parameters that are learned.

The MLP models use LeakyRELU (Maas et al., 2013) non-linearity between hidden layers. For model selection, we experimented with the different hyperparameters (Table 2) and used the ADAM (Kingma and Ba, 2014) optimizer. We utilised k-fold cross-validation with k=10 while training our models. One fold out of ten folds is chosen for validation, and nine folds are used for training. We applied k-fold cross-validation 40 times, with different configurations at each fold, to explore different combinations of hyperparameters and find the optimal model. We obtained 400 distinct models at the end. For M_{ANK} , we tested different model architectures (number of layers: {3, 4, 5, 6}, number of neurons: {16, 32, 48, 64}). For consistency, comparability, and ease of transfer learning, we used the same architecture for the other MLP models (of other cities). To further analyse the effects of TL, we also developed combined models namely $M_{ANK+IZM}$ (trained on D_{ANK} and D_{IZM}) and $M_{ANK+ERZ}$ (trained on D_{ANK} and D_{ERZ}). These combined models are trained with the building-related features used in the previous models as well as new features describing the climate of that particular city (HDD, DBT, and GHR -- Table 1).

2.3 Step III: Transfer Learning (TL)

TL is a method of adapting the weights of a pre-trained model for a new but related task, in order to exploit the knowledge obtained from a large dataset to improve the prediction performance on a small dataset. TL is suitable for our problem considering the small sizes of D_{IZM} and D_{ERZ} (Table 1). We applied TL on the source ML models (M_{ANK} , $M_{ANK+IZM}$, $M_{ANK+ERZ}$) for two target cities, D_{IZM} and D_{ERZ} . We used k-fold cross-validation with k=10 in this step, as we did in Step II. To observe the effect of dataset size on transfer learning as discussed in Step II, we fine-tuned the hyperparameters of M_{ANK} , $M_{ANK+IZM}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ}$ with different configurations to obtain $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$, respectively, where $\beta \in \{10, 30, 50\}$ (Table 2).

Table 2: Hyperparameter Configurations Considered for the ML Models

k-Fold Cross Validation	Learning Rate	Batch Size	Weight Decay	Number of Epochs
k=10	Uniform(10^{-6} , 10^{-2})	16, 32, 48, 64	Uniform(10^{-6} , 10^{-4})	20

3. Experiments and Results

In this section, we report the experiments and results analysing the performance of TL-based prediction of heating energy consumption. We first perform TL with all data available to us (Experiment 1) and then investigate the impact of the dataset size on the TL (Experiment 2).

3.1 Implementation and Training Details

We implemented our models with the PyTorch framework. We trained the models using the ADAM optimizer with L2 regularisation on the weights. We tuned the learning rate and regularisation strength within the specified intervals in Table 2. We evaluated the performances of the ML models with the conventional R^2 and Mean-Squared-Error (MSE) scores. We calculated R^2 and MSE scores for each fold and chose the models with the highest validation R^2 score from each fold. When training a model on multiple cities, we used the combination of the validation sets for the cities during cross-validation. We chose ten models in total, one from

each fold. Then, we calculated their average training, validation, testing R^2 , and MSE scores. Finally, we chose the model with the best average validation R^2 score to apply TL on.

3.2 Experiment 1: Transfer Learning

We first evaluate the performance of TL if all available data is used. The results are provided in Table 3. Before looking at the impact of TL, let us discuss the results of the models without any TL. We observe that M_{ANK} can predict $Q_{heating}$ on D_{ANK} with high accuracy (average test $R^2=0.986$). M_{IZM} 's predictions are less accurate (with average test $R^2=0.905$) on D_{IZM} , but it does not suffer from overfitting (with average train $R^2=0.929$) despite the small size of D_{IZM} . Similarly, M_{ERZ} predicted D_{ERZ} with less accuracy (with average test $R^2=0.932$) compared to M_{ANK} , and it also did not overfit the training data (with average train $R^2=0.961$) despite the small size of D_{ERZ} . We also note from Table 3 that combining datasets improves generalisation: $M_{ANK+IZM}$ predicted D_{ANK} and D_{IZM} accurately (with average test R^2 scores of 0.986 and 0.911, respectively), outperforming M_{IZM} on D_{IZM} . Similarly, $M_{ANK+ERZ}$ performed well on D_{ANK} and D_{ERZ} (with average test R^2 scores of 0.985 and 0.943, respectively), outperforming M_{ERZ} on D_{ERZ} .

If we look at the TL results in Table 3, we see that $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM}^{TL}$ outperformed M_{IZM} with its prediction performance on D_{IZM} (with an average test R^2 score of 0.911). Similarly, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ}^{TL}$ outperformed M_{ERZ} with its prediction performance on D_{ERZ} (with average test R^2 score of 0.935) (Figures 3 and 4). We also applied TL on combined datasets: We see that $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM}^{TL}$ outperformed both M_{IZM} and $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM}^{TL}$ with its prediction performance on D_{IZM} (with average test R^2 score of 0.916). On the other hand, $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ}^{TL}$ outperformed only M_{ERZ} with its prediction performance on D_{ERZ} (with an average test R^2 score of 0.932). (Figures 3 and 4). Furthermore, we observe that TL did not degrade the performance on the original dataset (results not provided here).

Table 3: The Prediction Qualities (Average Test R^2 Scores) of the ML Models.

ML Models	D_{IZM}				D_{ERZ}			
	$\Rightarrow IZM10$	$\Rightarrow IZM30$	$\Rightarrow IZM50$	$\Rightarrow IZM$	$\Rightarrow ERZ10$	$\Rightarrow ERZ30$	$\Rightarrow ERZ50$	$\Rightarrow ERZ$
M_{IZM}	0.852	0.891	0.895	0.905	-	-	-	-
M_{ERZ}	-	-	-	-	0.891	0.916	0.925	0.932
M_{ANK}^{TL}	0.898	0.906	0.907	0.911	0.916	0.930	0.933	0.935
$M_{ANK+IZM}$	-	-	-	0.911	-	-	-	-
$M_{ANK+IZM}^{TL}$	-	-	-	-	0.905	0.914	0.924	0.932
$M_{ANK+ERZ}$	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.943
$M_{ANK+ERZ}^{TL}$	0.898	0.905	0.910	0.916	-	-	-	-

3.3 Experiment 2: Impact of Dataset Size on Transfer Learning

Next, we evaluated the impact of dataset size on the contribution of transfer learning. To this end, we subsample the target dataset for different ratios and quantify how much transfer learning contributes in each case. If we look at the performances of the models without transfer

learning in Table 3, we see that the prediction accuracies of M_{IZM50} and M_{IZM30} on D_{IZM} were lower than but close to the prediction accuracy of M_{IZM} on D_{IZM} (with average test R^2 scores of 0.895 and 0.891, respectively) and they also did not overfit to the training data (with average train R^2 scores of 0.926 and 0.928, respectively). On the other hand, we observed an overfitting problem in M_{ERZ50} and M_{ERZ30} while predicting D_{ERZ} (with average train R^2 scores of 0.967 and 0.971, respectively), although they performed well on their testing datasets (with average test R^2 scores of 0.924 and 0.916, respectively). The overfitting problem became more evident in the prediction results of M_{IZM10} on D_{IZM} and M_{ERZ10} on D_{ERZ} . Their average test accuracies fell below 90%, and average train accuracies rose above 95% (Table 3). The increase in the overfitting problem can be better seen in Figures 3 and 4 for subsamples of D_{IZM} and M_{ERZ10} .

The main reason why models predicting subsampled datasets of D_{ERZ} encountered the overfitting problem earlier and more severe than those of D_{IZM} is that buildings present in D_{ERZ} have similar physical and thermal properties with each other. On the other hand, buildings in D_{IZM} have more diverse physical and thermal properties compared to those in D_{ERZ} .

To address the overfitting problem and improve the prediction performances of the ML models, we applied TL to M_{ANK} to obtain $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$. We also applied TL to $M_{ANK+IZM}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ}$ to obtain $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$. $\beta \in \{10, 30, 50\}$ in both of the experiments.

As shown in Table 3 and Figure 3, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ did provide better results than $M_{IZM \beta}$ with their prediction performances on D_{IZM} . In other words, TL to Izmir from Ankara or Ankara + Erzurum performed better than a model trained only in Izmir. Although $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ had lower average train R^2 scores than $M_{IZM \beta}$, they made better generalisations during training processes without overfitting to their corresponding training dataset. $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ outperformed $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ on D_{IZM} for $\beta = 50$. However, their results were similar for $\beta \in \{10, 30\}$.

Similarly, as shown in Table 3 and Figure 4, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ performed better than $M_{ERZ \beta}$ with its prediction performance on D_{ERZ} . Similar to our previous observations on $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ made better generalisations than $M_{ERZ \beta}$ during training without overfitting to their corresponding training dataset. On the other hand, $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM \beta}^{TL}$ performed more poorly than $M_{ERZ \beta}$ on D_{ERZ} for $\beta \in \{50, 30\}$ and $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ for $\beta \in \{50, 30\}$. $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ outperformed $M_{ERZ \beta}$ on D_{ERZ} only for $\beta \in \{10\}$. Similar to $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$, $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ encountered an overfitting problem less severe than $M_{ERZ \beta}$ for $\beta \in \{50, 30, 10\}$.

The insufficient contribution of $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ can be attributed to the discrepancy of Izmir buildings compared to those in Erzurum. Although $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$ did perform better than M_{ERZ} , using the distribution of data in D_{IZM} degrades the performance of $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ \beta}^{TL}$.

To conclude, in the case of low-data settings, it can be beneficial to apply transfer learning on models trained on cities with larger datasets.

Figure 3: Comparison on the performances of $M_{IZM\beta}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow IZM\beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+ERZ \Rightarrow IZM\beta}^{TL}$ on $D_{IZM\beta}$

Figure 4: Comparison on the performances of $M_{ERZ\beta}$, $M_{ANK \Rightarrow ERZ\beta}^{TL}$ and $M_{ANK+IZM \Rightarrow ERZ\beta}^{TL}$ on $D_{ERZ\beta}$

4. Conclusion and Discussion

In this paper, we focused on the problem of estimating energy consumption in cities using machine learning. To be specific, we proposed using transfer learning to improve the prediction accuracy of energy consumption in target cities. To this end, we collected building energy modelling data from three different cities and trained multi-layer perceptrons on different cities with and without transfer learning.

Our extensive experiments showed that transfer learning is able to utilise what has been learned in a source city for a target city and that this provides better performance than a machine learning model trained from scratch. We further analysed and demonstrated that this benefit is especially significant if the amount of data on the target city is scarce.

Limitations & Future Work

Although our results highlight the promise of transfer learning for UBEM, we note that our work can be extended in different ways. For example, other types of machine learning models and deep learning architectures can be probed for transfer learning for UBEM. Furthermore, considering the discrepancy between the distributions of buildings across different cities, it is worth performing experiments with more cities with more diverse building and climate distributions.

Acknowledgments

This study is funded by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK) under grant number 22AG019 and Horizon Europe under grant number 101096405. We gratefully acknowledge the computational resources provided by resources kindly provided by TUBITAK ULAKBIM High Performance and Grid Computing Center (TRUBA) and METU Robotics and Artificial Intelligence Center (ROMER).

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